

Research protocol

For the paper entitled: *“Give Software Developers Time”:
Investigating Perceived Performance and Stress in a Com-
pressed Work Schedule*

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1. Interviews

In this section, we provide the information how we created the interview guidelines per team and furthermore, the interview guidelines itself. We start with Team Tsubasa.

a. Team Tsubasa

The interviews aimed to assess both performance capacity and perceived stress levels, as well as to investigate the utilization of the "Plus-Day." However, the primary focus was on answering the third research question concerning how the Plus-Day is utilized. Addressing the first two research questions served primarily to validate findings obtained through other data collection methods.

In accordance with the project's scope, at the case organization was selected as the object of investigation. In total, five employees and one team leader participated in the interviews.

To protect the participants' privacy and confidentiality, interview data was anonymized during the evaluation. Furthermore, to preserve individual anonymity, the following introductory questions were removed:

- E1: In which work areas are you active, and how long have you been working there?
- E2: What is your role in this work area?

We opted for semi-structured interviews, a well-established method suitable for application in case studies. Compared to unstructured interviews, this format allows for a structured and predictable flow of questions, necessary in our study for gaining approval of the questionnaire by the works council prior to the interviews. At the same time, semi-structured interviews provide sufficient flexibility for improvisation and deeper exploration of emerging topics during the conversation (Runeson & Höst, 2009)

GQM Documentation:

Using the Goal Question Metric (GQM), we developed an interview guide containing specific questions to answer the research questions (RQ1 to RQ3). The Goal Question Metric (GQM) is a methodological approach in research aimed at defining clear and measurable objectives for an investigation (Basili, 1994 & Dalton, 2019). Additionally, we employed the hourglass principle, where initial questions are more open-ended, questions in the middle become more closed, and questions towards the end of the interview again become more open-ended (Runeson & Höst, 2009). The following figures illustrate the outcomes of the GQM.

Figure 1: Goal-Questions derivation tree for RQ 1 (Team Tsubasa)

Figure 2: Goal-Questions derivation tree for RQ 2 (Team Tsubasa)

Figure 3: Goal-Questions derivation tree for RQ 3 (Team Tsubasa)

Interview Guideline:

Warm-Up	Welcome to today's interview, and thank you very much for taking the time to participate.
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Information phase	<p>My colleague is ... and my name is We are ... from the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Hannover.</p>
	<p>Our group is conducting a research project investigating the effects of introducing a Plus-Day workweek in an organizational unit. Several research questions will be addressed during this interview:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RQ1: How does the (perceived) performance capacity change? • RQ2: How does the (perceived) stress level change? • RQ3: What is the „Plus-Day“ used for?
	<p>The main focus today is on the third research question.</p>
	<p>Do you agree to the recording of this interview? The audio recording will only be used for transcription purposes. Your statements will remain anonymous.</p>
Opening Questions	<p>To start, could you please tell us a little more about yourself?</p>
	<p>Q1: In which work areas are you active, and how long have you been working there?</p> <p>Q2: What role do you have in this work area?</p> <p>Q3: Have you previously considered the idea of a 4/Plus-Day workweek, and what is your general opinion about it?</p>
Main Interview	
<i>RQ1: How does perceived performance change under a compressed work schedule?</i>	<p>Q4: Are there already performance metrics used in your organizational unit? If yes, which ones?</p> <p>Q5: Did you manage to accomplish the same tasks in more or less time?</p> <p>Q5.1: Is this reflected in the metrics?</p> <p>Q6: Due to the reduced time, were measures taken to create more space for accomplishing the most relevant tasks? (Tip: e.g., reducing meeting durations)</p> <p>Q6.1: If yes, how did this impact your performance capacity?</p> <p>Q6.2: Did this lead to new processes or measures that could continue after the project ends?</p>

<p>RQ2: How does the (perceived) stress level change?</p>	<p>Q7: Do you feel that the Plus-Day workweek has influenced your perceived stress level? If yes, how? Q7.1: What factors caused these effects?</p>
<p>RQ3: What are the organizational benefits of the Plus-Day</p> <p>--> Focus of these interviews</p>	<p>Q8: What activities have already been carried out on the Plus-Day? Q9: How was the decision made about which activities to undertake on the Plus-Day? Q10: Were these activities conducted in the office, in an external environment, or remotely? Q11: Are the Plus-Day activities oriented towards team building or work-related/organizational content? Q12: What other activities would you like to see on the Plus-Day? Q13: How was the operability of managed systems ensured on the Plus-Day? (On-call/emergencies) Q13.1: Are there already concepts covering these scenarios? Q14: Is there a need for training regarding systems that will be introduced in the near future? Q14.1: Could these training sessions take place on the Plus-Day? Q15: What dependencies exist with employees who are not participating in the Plus-Day workweek? Q15.1: Do these dependencies influence the activities that can be performed on the Plus-Day?</p>
<p>Closing questions</p>	<p>CQ1: What was your motivation to participate in the Plus-Day workweek? CQ2: What were your expectations, and to what extent have these been fulfilled?</p>

	CQ3: Are there any additional questions or remarks from your side about points not yet mentioned, but that seem important to you?
	Finally, we would like to thank you again for your time and wish you a pleasant day.

Table 1: Interview Guideline for Team Tsubasa

b. Team Wakabayashi (Organization Nankatsu SC)

The interview guide was created using the Goal Question Metric (GQM). We derived the objectives for the interview based on the three given research questions, with the main focus on FF3. The results for FF1 and FF2 were to be validated by the semi-structured interviews. The following questions were derived from the given objectives and the information on the planned events of Team Wakabayashi and clustered using metrics.

Topic areas	Metrics
Introduction	
Team Building	Team collaboration and organization
Professional training	Personal / team development
Optimization / Quality of Life	Prozess optimization and tool integration
Operations	
Other activities	
Performance (perceived)	Performance
Perceived Stress	Stress

Table 2: Topic areas and metrics derived for Team Wakabayashi

InterviewerIn:	
Teilnehmer:	Anonymisiert
Datum:	
Ort:	Vor-Ort/virtuell
Dauer:	30-45 Minuten
Interviewmethode:	Semi-strukturiert

- I. **Begrüßung und Einstieg:**
 - Befragte Person begrüßen und für die Teilnahme bedanken
 - (Kurze) Vorstellung des Interviewers

- II. **Ziel des Interviews:** Untersuchung der Auswirkungen experimentell eingeführter 4+-Tage-Wochen auf agile Softwareentwicklungsteams
Adressierung der Forschungsfrage: Wofür wird der Plus-Tag genutzt?

- III. **Freiwilligkeit:** Wenn immer Sie etwas nicht tun wollen, müssen Sie selbstverständlich nicht. Sie können das Interview jederzeit abbrechen, falls Sie sich dabei nicht wohl fühlen. Wichtig: Das hat selbstverständlich keine Nachteile oder Folgen!

- IV. **Aufzeichnung:** Ist es für Sie in Ordnung, wenn das Interview aufgezeichnet wird, damit wir das Gespräch anschliessend transkribieren und auswerten können?

- V. **Vertraulichkeit:** Ihre Angaben sind natürlich vertraulich. Ihre Aussagen werden anonymisiert und nicht mit Ihrem Namen veröffentlicht. Somit wird niemand ausser Ihnen oder uns erfahren, was Sie in diesem Interview gesagt haben.

- VI. **Einverständniserklärung (mündlich erläutern):**

Haben Sie noch Fragen bevor wir einsteigen?

Figure 4: Interview Introduction Protocol Template (Team Wakabayashi)

Interview Guideline:

<p>Warm-Up</p>	<p>What was your motivation to participate in the Plus-Day experiment? What expectations did you have?</p>
<p>Main Interview</p>	
<p><i>Cluster 1: Team building (Metrics Team collaboration and organization)</i></p>	<p>TF2.1 How was it decided what activities should take place on the Plus Day? TF2.2 Did the activities only take place on site or remotely? TF2.2.1 If both, which setting do you prefer? TF2.3 What did the team building activities look like before the Plus Day? TF2.4 What do the measures look like now that Plus Days have been introduced? TF2.4.1 Are there any restrictions on the part of the employer? TF2.5 Has the co-operation between the Plus Day participants changed positively? TF2.6 How has the cooperation between the non-participants and the Plus Day participants changed? TF2.7 Do the non-participants have an influence on the activities of the Plus Day?</p>
<p><i>Cluster 2: Professional training (Metric: Personal / team development)</i></p>	<p>TF3.1 Have training courses been held on the Plus Day to date? TF3.1.1 If yes: On which topic(s) did the training take place? TF3.1.2 How long did the training last? TF3.1.3 Was the training online or on site? TF3.1.3.1 If online, which platform was used? TF3.1.4 Has the knowledge acquired during the training already been actively applied in everyday work? TF3.2 Have private programming projects taken place so far? TF3.2.1 If yes: Have new tools been used? TF3.2.1.1 If yes: Which tools were used? TF3.2.1.2 Can you imagine integrating the (new) tool into your daily work routine instead of the current one?</p>

<p>Cluster 3: Optimization / Quality of Life (Prozess optimization and tool integration)</p>	<p>TF4.1 Were internal departmental processes reflected on the Plus Day?</p> <p>TF4.1.1 If yes: Were processes categorised as requiring improvement?</p> <p>TF4.1.1.1 If yes: Were measures introduced to optimise these processes?</p> <p>TF4.1.1.1.1 If yes: Which tools were used for optimisation?</p> <p>TF4.2 Were cross-departmental processes reflected on the Plus Day?</p> <p>TF4.2.1 If yes: Were processes categorised as requiring improvement?</p> <p>TF4.2.1.1 If yes: Have measures been introduced to optimise these processes?</p> <p>TF4.2.1.1.1 If yes: Which tools were used for optimisation?</p> <p>TF4.3 Have new tools been implemented for everyday use as a result of the plus tag?</p>
<p>Cluster 4: Operations</p>	<p>TF5.1 How was the operability of the systems/applications to be supported ensured on the plus day?</p> <p>TF5.1.1 Is there a standby plan in the event of malfunctions?</p>
<p>Cluster 5: Other activities</p>	<p>TF6.1 Did you carry out any other activities during the Plus Day that have not yet been mentioned?</p> <p>TF6.1.1 If yes: Which activities took place?</p> <p>TF6.1.2 If no: Why not?</p>
<p>Cluster 6: Performance (perceived) (Metric: Performance)</p>	<p>TF7.1 Does your organisational unit use metrics to measure performance?</p> <p>TF7.1.1 If yes, which ones?</p> <p>TF7.2 Were you able to manage the weekly tasks despite the plus day?</p> <p>TF7.2.1 If yes, were they able to complete more tasks than before the Plus Day was introduced?</p> <p>TF7.3 How do you think your performance has changed?</p>

Cluster 7: Perceived stress (Metric: Stress)	<p>TF8.1 From your point of view, has your perception of stress changed?</p> <p>TF8.1.1 If yes, has it changed positively or negatively?</p> <p>TF8.1.2 What factors triggered the change?</p>
Closing	<p>TF9.1 How did you feel about the Plus Days in general?</p> <p>TF9.1.1 Were your expectations met?</p> <p>TF9.2 Should the Plus Day be continued?</p> <p>TF9.2.1 If yes, what activities would you like to see on the Plus Day?</p> <p>TF9.3 Do you have any questions or comments?</p> <p>Thank you very much for your valuable time!</p>

Table 3: Interview Guideline for Team Wakabayashi

c. Team Hyuga (Organization Toho Academy)

Figure 5: Goal-Questions derivation tree example for RQ 1 (Team Hyuga)

Interview Guideline:

<p>Warm-Up</p>	<p>Introduction of the interviewer and the research project, information about the interview process</p>
<p>Main Interview</p> <p><i>Cluster 1.1 Performance capacity (Metric: Performance/Productivity)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial question 1: Do you measure or evaluate performance? - Initial question 2: Which metrics (how?) are used and what (e.g. number of applications processed, customer satisfaction, etc.) is measured? - Question 1.1.1.1: Are you achieving all the objectives of your work? - Question 1.1.1.2: Are the tasks easy for you? - FF2: How has your subjective perception of stress changed in recent times (since the start of the experiment)? - Question 1.1.1.3: Do you perform well in your work? - Supplements: How does the 4+day working week affect your productivity? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Focus/concentration o Motivation o Work habits o Performance, pressure
<p><i>Cluster 1.2: Performance capacity (Motivation / Willingness to perform)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Question 1.1.2.1: Has your motivation changed during the 4+ day week compared to the regular 5-day week? If so, in what way? - Question 1.1.2.2: Were there certain factors during the 4+ day week that influenced your motivation? - Question 1.1.2.2.a: If so, how exactly and to what do you attribute this? - Question 1.1.2.2.b: If not, what do you think are the reasons for this?
<p><i>Cluster 3.1: Plus-Day Benefits on personal level (Metrics Personal development, motivation,</i></p>	<p>Metric 3.1.1: Personal development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Question 3.1.1.1: What potential do you see for your professional development in your current field of activity? - Question 3.1.1.2: What potential do you see for your further development in relation to your current field of activity?

<p>positive attitude, well-being</p>	<p>Metric 3.1.2: Motivation (or willingness to contribute ideas)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Question 3.1.2.1: Has your motivation in relation to work changed as a result of the 4+ day week? - Question 3.1.2.1.a: If yes, how exactly (positive/negative) and to what do you attribute this? - Question 3.1.2.1.b: If no, what do you think are the reasons for this? <p>Other ideas for questions on motivation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How did the 4+ day week change your motivation? - Were there certain factors or events that influenced your motivation during the 4+ day week? - Can you give examples of when you felt particularly motivated or demotivated during the 4+ day week and why? <p>Metric 3.1.3: (Positive) attitude towards life / personal well-being / problems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Question 3.1.3.1: Has your attitude to life or your personal well-being changed during the 4+ day week? - Question 3.1.3.1.a: If yes, how exactly (positive/negative) and to what do you attribute this? - Question 3.1.3.1.b: If no, what do you think are the reasons for this? - Question 3.1.3.2: Were there certain factors or events that had a positive or negative effect on your mood and well-being? - Question 3.1.3.3: Can you give examples of when you felt particularly happy, satisfied or balanced during the 4+ day week and why? If not, what do you attribute this to?
<p>Cluster 3.2: Plus-Day Benefits on organizational level (Metrics: team work, working atmosphere, organizational culture)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Question 3.2.1.1: Has collaboration within your team changed during the 4+ day week? - Question 3.2.1.1a: If yes, how exactly (positive/negative) and to what do you attribute this? - Question 3.2.1.1b: If no, what do you think are the reasons for this?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Question 3.2.1.2: Has the efficiency of team meetings changed? - Question 3.2.1.2a: If yes, in what way and to what do you attribute this? - Question 3.2.1.2b: If not, what could be the reasons for this? - Question 3.2.2.1: Has the social relationship with your work colleagues changed? - Question 3.2.2.1a: If yes, in what form and what is the reason for this? - Question 3.2.2.1b: If not, what could be the reasons for this?
Closing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 'We are slowly approaching the end of our conversation. As final questions, I would like to know ...?' - What is your motivation for taking part in this experiment? - Can you imagine a permanent introduction of the 4+day working week? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o If yes/no, what are the decisive aspects for you? o If no, are there aspects of the 4+ day week that should be retained? (e.g. regular team-building activities, excursions, ...) - Beyond my questions, is there anything else you would like to share with me? For example, did you expect a specific question that was not asked in this interview? - Do you have any questions for me or anything else you would like to add?

2. Interview Data Analysis

Here, we provide the results from our data analysis activities and provide the information for Team Tsubasa (Organization Nankatsu SC).

The recorded interviews were transcribed using Whisper AI (Whisper 2023). Whisper AI is an automated transcription software based on artificial intelligence that converts audio files into text using speech recognition technology (cf. Spiller et al. 2023, p. 2). The transcripts were presented to the interviewed employees for review and subsequently approved by them. Relevant statements were then assigned to the corresponding research questions. The grouped results were visualized on a Miro board to identify relationships and patterns. This grouping allowed for verification of consistency among statements.

Figure 6: Coding scheme example (Team Tsubasa)

The insights from these interviews are presented in the following figures, which are excerpts from the Miro board. Each note includes the research question, the anonymized participant, the text line from the transcription, and the corresponding statement. The pattern can be described as follows: Initially, interview results were assigned to the respective research questions using different colors (violet, cyan, and green). Additionally, uncategorized responses (marked in purple) were sorted into "Other Interesting Statements" (see Fig. 22). For the first research question (see Fig. 12 to Fig. 15), the responses were subdivided into "Performance has increased," "Performance remained the same," "Performance has decreased," and "Other."

Figure 7: Coding result for improved performance (Team Tsubasa)

Figure 8: Coding result for stable performance (Team Tsubasa)

Sonstiges

F1.E.195-196
Aktuell keine
Metriken zur
Leistungserfas-
sung

F1.E.201-202
Bewertung der
Leistungssteigeru-
ng anhand
Mitarbeitergesprä-
chen

F1.E.201-202
Teilnehmer E kann
seine
Leistungsfähigkeit nicht
wirklich beurteilen, da
er recht neu in der
Abteilung ist

F1.F.207-209
Keine Metriken
erlaubt und
Betriebsrat ist
da aufmerksam

F1.F.225-227
Keine
Maßnahmen zum
Zeitschaffen in
kürzerer Woche
durchgeführt

F1.F.258-270
4+ Tag sollte
prinzipiell
beibehalten werden,
da es bisher nur
Vorteile gab

F1.F.260-270
Alternativ ab
Freitagmittag einen Slot
schaffen für z.B.
individuelle
Weiterbildungen oder
normal weiterarbeiten

F1.C.343
Es gibt eine
Zeiterfassung wer wie
lange an einem Projekt
gearbeitet hat aber da
trägt jeder ein was am
besten passt

F1.E.294-301
Durch den 4+Tag kann die
Arbeit voll verbessert
werden (muss nicht
beobachtet werden wie es
sich entwickelt). Da
Prozesse hinterfragt sind
neue Sachen gelernt
werden.

F1.D.371-374
Optimierung von
Prozessen am 4+Tag
könnte langfristig
für schneller
Aufgaben erfüllen
sorgen

Figure 9: Coding result for other statements wrt. performance (Team Tsubasa)

Figure 10: Coding result for increased perceived stress (Team Tsubasa)

Figure 11: Coding result for decreased perceived stress (Team Tsubasa)

Figure 12: Coding result for other statements wrt. stress (Team Tsubasa)

Figure 13: Coding result for statements wrt. Plus-Day Activities (Team Tsubasa)

3. Observation Data Analysis

Here, we provide the results from our data analysis activities. As with the first section, we present the information team-by-team starting with Team Tsubasa.

a. Team Tsubasa (Organization Nankatsu SC)

A template was created to conduct observations, known as the observation protocol. This protocol contains fundamental information about each observation, such as date, location, participants, planned/actual duration, research questions, observer, event, and context. Additionally, the observation protocol includes targeted questions designed to extract relevant insights from all observed events (cf. Merklinger 2022, p. 47). The following targeted questions were formulated concerning our research questions:

1. Are the employees stressed during the event? If so, how is this manifested?
2. Are the employees motivated during the event? If so, how is this manifested?
3. Do all employees actively participate during the event? If not, what could be the reasons?
4. Is the team's mood positive during the event?
5. Are there communication problems within the team during the event? If so, how were these resolved?

The observation protocol provides space for recording observed events through a table consisting of the columns "Time," "(Conversational) Actions," and "Subjective Impressions." This structure allows the observer to distinguish between what is seen/heard and their own impressions during the observation itself (cf. Merklinger 2022, p. 47). Afterwards, conversational actions and subjective impressions are evaluated and summarized in the field labeled "Evaluation."

The following section describes the procedure for the conducted observations. Observations were always performed in pairs, and insights gathered during the observations were documented in observation protocols.

Initially, two observations were conducted in a digital setting, scheduled within the same week on Monday and Friday. Given that the 4-Plus-Day usually occurred on Thursdays, one observation took place before and one after this event. These VIKO meetings represent daily coordination sessions, where the team gathers to discuss current issues and organizational matters. Scheduled for 30 minutes, meeting durations varied depending on the number of topics discussed. Each observation covered the entire length of the scheduled meeting. As these meetings were daily occurrences, not all team members were always present. Meetings were conducted with webcams, and the observers also had their cameras on, ensuring employees were constantly aware they were being observed.

The on-site observation took place at the company's premises. At this point, some employees already knew the observers from previous digital meetings. This observation was conducted during a 4-Plus-Day and scheduled for four hours. It should be noted that the observation occurred immediately before a public holiday, resulting in many employees having at least the next day or even two days off. Upon arrival, observers were greeted by two employees at the entrance and escorted to the room where the team conducted their 4-Plus-Day. Observers were seated at the edge of the room but positioned as if integrated into the event, making employees continually aware of the observation.

Observation results were analyzed and assigned to the corresponding research questions. F1, F2, F3 correspond respectively to research questions 1, 2, and 3. FX refers to general findings that could not be clearly assigned to any specific research question. The following two figures illustrate the observation findings aligned with the research questions.

Figure 14: Coding result of the on-site observation protocols data (Team Tsubasa)

Figure 15: Coding result of the virtual observation protocols data (Team Tsubasa)

b. Team Wakabayashi (Organization Nankatsu SC)

Due to data protection regulations, we are not able to provide as detailed informations as for Team Tsubasa.

c. Team Hyuga (Organization Toho Academy)

Due to data protection regulations, we are not able to provide as detailed informations as for Team Tsubasa.

Appendix A) Survey (PSQ & IWPQ) Raw Data

The raw data from the PSQ and IWPQ surveys can be provided upon request, please contact michael.neumann@hs-hannover.de.

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